

Code of Conduct

The Swiss Research Data Support Network (SRDSN) is a network for research data support professionals. The Code of Conduct (CoC) ensures that the values of the network are adhered to. All SRDSN members and guests that join the SRDSN network are asked to agree and adhere to the rules outlined in this CoC.

1 SRDSN Culture, Standards and Values

We strive to ensure that we have a welcoming, inclusive, trustworthy, respectful, transparent, collaborative and open atmosphere in our community.

1.1 Diversity, Openness and Inclusivity

We seek diversity of views. We respect and encourage all voices. We help and support network members to actively listen and to be heard. We facilitate inclusive interactions by welcoming, respecting and encouraging participation from everyone, whether on-site or online, regardless of the person's native language, institutional affiliation, or other differences. We encourage all members to actively participate in discussions, while encouraging others to join in, so all voices can be heard. We embrace cultural diversity and promote a multicultural environment.

1.2 Respect and Empathy

We aim to communicate in an open, honest and direct way, so that people feel comfortable and welcome. We respectfully acknowledge the opinions, work and contributions of others.

If a member decides to withdraw from the SRDSN Community, they should take the necessary steps to ensure that other members can continue their work / role. In doing so, departing members treat those who remain in the network with respect and do not endanger the goals or accomplishments of the community.

1.3 Curiosity

Discovering new topics and ideas driven by curiosity fosters the community. Therefore, proposing new topics and ideas is highly encouraged and welcomed.

1.4 Collaboration and Support

At SRDSN, we support each other in our endeavour to deliver professional Research Data Management (RDM) services. We welcome members with a strong interest in RDM so that they can build and improve on established work.

2 Communication and Dissemination

2.1 Communication

All communication should be appropriate to a professional audience consisting of people from diverse backgrounds.

Harassment will not be tolerated, this includes but is not limited to, offensive verbal or written comments related to any of the following: gender, gender identity and expression, age, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, body size, colour, ethnicity and nationality, native language, religion, financial and family status, or other attributes as well as other dimensions of diversity. This also includes sustained disruption of talks, inappropriate physical contact, and unwelcome sexual attention.

We recognize that disagreements may arise, but these should never result in personal attacks that can insult, demean or belittle others. All discussions and debates should be conducted respectfully and professionally with a focus on issues, not persons.

2.2 Presentations and Publications

Participants of SRDSN meetings and events should comply with the [Code of Conduct for Scientific Integrity of the Swiss Academies](#) and respect personal rights as well as intellectual property rights of other persons.

Members should as well refrain from publishing or posting materials that:

- include statements that are bigoted, hateful or racially offensive;
- advocate for illegal activities;
- contain vulgar, obscene or indecent language or images;
- are defamatory, abusive, or threatening;
- contain personal information (e.g., names, address, phone number, email) of other persons unless explicit informed consent is given by that concerned person and is in compliance with the applicable data protection laws.

Subject to any third-party rights, we encourage sharing the results of the network's activities beyond the network while acknowledging the work of others and acknowledging the SRDSN (e.g., on the SRDSN website).

3 Misconduct and Violations

If a member engages in any harmful or inappropriate behavior, such as harassment, offensive comments and/or personal attacks that infringe on this CoC, the Steering Committee (SC) may take the following measures:

3.1 Warning

A violation of the CoC can occur through a single incident or a series of actions. In such cases, the SC will warn the member about the consequences of continuing this behavior. This may include a request for the individual to avoid any interaction with and maintain distance from the person harmed by their behavior, as well as those members of the SC enforcing the CoC, for a specified period. Failure to comply with these terms may result in a temporary or permanent ban.

3.2 Temporary Ban

In the case of a severe violation of the SRDSN values and standards, especially if involving sustained inappropriate behavior, the SC may impose a temporary ban on the individual's SRDSN membership. During this ban, the member is prohibited from any interaction or communication with the community for a specified duration. Additionally, no public or private interaction with the involved parties, including unsolicited interactions with those enforcing the Code of Conduct, is permitted during this time. Violating these terms may lead to a permanent membership ban.

This has no effect on other network members of the same institution.

3.3 Permanent Ban

Demonstrating a pattern of violation of the SRDSN values and standards, including sustained inappropriate behavior, harassment, or aggression will lead to a permanent ban from the SRDSN by the SC and the cancellation of the individual membership.

This has no effect on other network members of the same institution.

4 Reporting

If you feel unsafe or unwelcome at any SRDSN events, or if you witness a violation of the CoC, please report this as soon as possible to the SC.

The privacy of all parties will be guaranteed.

5 Review of the Code of Conduct

The code of conduct will be reviewed regularly by the SC, based on feedback from SRDSN members and in line with accepted CoC developments.